

PROJECT MANAGEMENT HANDBOOK

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D.6.1: Project Management Handbook

WP6. T.6.1: Management and steering of the project

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Dynamo Project Management Handbook

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1. Technical References

1.1. Project General Information

Project Number	101046489
Project Acronym	Dynamo
Project Title	Dynamic Spatio-Temporal Modulation of Light by Phononic Architectures
Granting Authority	European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency
Call	HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN-01
Topic	HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN-01-01
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PIC of the Lead beneficiary	999882985
Contributing beneficiary/ies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC) - Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS) - Akademia Górniczo-Hutnicza Im. Stanisława Staszica W Krakowie (AGH)
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V1	11/07/2022	UJI	Daniel Torrent
	Date	Beneficiary	Reviewed by
V2	20/07/2022	CSIC, CNRS, AGH	Agustín Mihi, Bernard Bonello and Pawel Packo
	Date	Beneficiary	Approved by
V3	25/07/2022	UJI	Daniel Torrent

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3. Introduction

3.1.Executive Summary

The present document is the deliverable D6.1- “Project Management Handbook” of the Dynamo project, funded by the European Commission’s European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA), under its Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme (HE).

The aim of this Project Management Handbook, as a reference document for Dynamo participants, is to give an overall perspective of the most relevant managerial aspects, procedures, rules, and responsibilities of the consortium aiming at ensuring a successful project execution. In addition, its purpose is to complement the legally binding documents: Consortium Agreement and Grant Agreement.

This document summarizes all the needed knowledge for the correct management of the project and contains all information related to the management strategy, structure of the management team, monitoring and reporting issues, and the contractual and financial follow-up with the European Commission.

The handbook should be updated, when necessary, through the lifecycle of the Dynamo project and according to the project needs. Whenever the procedures are updated, all partners will be duly informed about the changes made with respect to the previous version, and participants shall agree on including additional information and processes.

3.2.Relation to Other Project Documents

In the event of discrepancy between documents, this Project Management Handbook is overruled by Grant Agreement including its Annexes and the Consortium Agreement with its possible addendums.

3.3.Abbreviation List

This is the list of the acronyms that are used in the present document:

- EISMEA: European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency
- EIC: European Innovation Council
- EC: European Commission
- GA: Grant Agreement
- CA: Consortium Agreement
- WP: Work Packages
- RP: Reporting Period
- PCC: Project Coordination Committee
- AB: Advisory Board
- OG: Observer Group
- IPR: Intellectual Property Rights
- MIM: Mutual Insurance Mechanism
- DoA: Description of the Action
- CFS: Certificate on the Financial Statements

- SyGMA: System for Grant Management

3.4. Reference Documents

This handbook is based on the following reference documents:

- Dynamo Grant Agreement No.101046489
- Dynamo Consortium Agreement
- General Model Grant Agreement EIC Accelerator Contract (HE MGA - Multi & Mono): https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/agr-contr/general-mga_horizon-euratom_en.pdf
- EU Funding Programmes 2021-2027 Online Manual: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/om_en.pdf

4. Project Basis

4.1. Participants

The list of Dynamo participants is included in the Grant Agreement, in the Consortium Agreement, and presented in the next list:

No.	Participant Organization	Short Name	Country	Role
1	Universitat Jaume I	UJI	Spain	Coordinator
2	Fundación Universitat Jaume I- Empresa	FUE	Spain	Affiliated Entity
3	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	CSIC	Spain	Beneficiary
4	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique CNRS	CNRS	France	Beneficiary
5	Akademia Górniczo-Hutnicza Im. Stanisława Staszica W Krakowie	AGH	Poland	Beneficiary
6	Association Européenne des Agences de Développement	EURADA	Belgium	Associated Partner
7	Fundación para el Fomento de la Investigación Sanitaria y Biomédica de la Comunitat Valenciana	FISABIO	Spain	Associated Partner
8	Instituto Valenciano de la Competitividad Empresarial	IVACE	Spain	Associated Partner

9	Finnovaregio	FINNOVA	Belgium	Associated Partner
10	Institut d'électronique de Microélectronique et de Nanotechnologie	IEMN	France	Associated Partner
11	Université Pierre et Marie Curie	UPMC	France	Associated Partner
12	Holoeye Photonics AG	HOLOEYE	Germany	Associated Partner
13	Sorbonne Université	SORBONNE	France	Associated Partner
14	Imperial College of Science Technology and Medicine	IC	United Kingdom	Party

Table 1: List of Participants

4.2. Duration, Budget, and EC Contribution

The effective start of the project is 01.03.2022, and the project ends **48 months** later, on 28.02.2026.

The project has an overall budget of **2,552,277.50 €** and the funding rate is 100%, thus, all costs shall be financed by the European Commission.

The budget detailed per beneficiary and the corresponding EU contribution of each beneficiary is detailed in the Annex 2 to the Grant Agreement – Estimated budget of the action.

The EC contribution of each of the partners is a maximum contribution conditioned to the acceptance by the EC of expenses up to the budget of the partner (this means that if a partner spends less than what it is shown in its approved budget (or the Commission does not accept all its costs), it will receive only the proportional part of the EC contribution).

4.3. Contractual Documents

Grant Agreement

Grant Agreement with the EC: Grant Agreement No. 101046489. This is the contractual document signed by all the project partners which defines the rights and obligations of the Consortium regarding the EC. The Grant Agreement includes the following annexes:

- Annex 1 - Description of the action (DoA): This is the contractual document which describes the work to be performed by the Consortium.
- Annex 2 - Estimated Budget for the Action
- Annex 3 - Accession Form for Beneficiaries
- Annex 4 - Model for the Financial Statements

- Annex 5 - Specific Rules

The Grant Agreement and its annexes will be available for all partners in the private intranet in the project website (<https://dynamo-project.eu/>).

Grant Agreement Amendments

Amendments to the Grant Agreement may reflect the need to adapt to the changing conditions for implementation of the action. For more detailed information about conditions and procedures for amendments to the G.A see section 9.1 of this document.

Consortium Agreement

The Consortium Agreement is defined as an internal contract among the consortium partners which is signed and accepted by all partners. It defines the rights and obligations of the project partners and contains provisions about organization and decision-making, financial questions, and the handling of intellectual property rights within the consortium.

In case of discrepancy, the Consortium Agreement is overruled by the Grant Agreement.

The project Consortium Agreement will be also available for all partners in the private intranet in the project website (<https://dynamo-project.eu/>).

5. Project Structure

The plan of the project follows the tasks and activities and schedule as laid down in the Work Plan (Data Sheet to the GA, section 4). The guiding point of all work and planning will be the Deliverables due to the Commission along the **3 reporting periods** of:

- RP1: from month 1 to month 12
- RP2: from month 13 to month 30
- RP3: from month 31 to month 48

5.1. Work Packages

Dynamo is a 48-month project organized in **7 Work Packages**. The detailed description of each Work Package is described in pages 75 - 80 of the GA.

The following table includes the list of WPs as indicates the partner responsible of each of them.

No.	WP Title	Lead Beneficiary	Effort (Person-Months)	Start Month	End Month
WP1	Modelling of phononic surfaces	1 – UJI	63,00	1	24
WP2	Optimization of vibrational mode density	4 - AGH / AGH-UST	80,00	18	42
WP3	Fabrication of Phononic Architectures	2 - CSIC	106,00	1	48
WP4	Sample characterization	3 - CNRS	52,00	1	48

WP5	Application development	1 – UJI	50,00	1	48
WP6	Management	1 – UJI	42,50	1	48
WP7	Dissemination	1 – UJI	24,50	1	48

Table 2: List of Work Packages

Each Work Package has a WP Leader that is the partner responsible for the coordination of the technical and financial aspects of the correspondent WP. This includes the preparation of any technical reports, achieving milestones, achieving deliverables and provision of deliverables and progress reports to the coordinator.

5.2. Deliverables

Each WP will have deliverables associated to, which shall be rigorously submitted to the EC. In the table below, the list of deliverables for the 48 months of the project is shown in chronological order, to make it easy to follow up on deliverable submission.

If deliverable must be updated and submitted in different dates, the deliverables is shown as many times as dates, with the indication of the release month (month #). For those deliverables that have more than one version, but the different dates are not fixed, the delivery is shown once.

Del. No	Deliverable Name	WP No	Lead Beneficiary	Type ¹	Dissemination Level ²	Due Date (month)
D7.1	Project website and social media profiles	WP7	1 – UJI	DEC – Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	PU - Public	2
D3.1	Provide a set of calibration samples	WP3	2 – CSIC	R – Document, report	SEN – Sensitive	3
D6.1	Project Management Handbook	WP6	1 – UJI	R – Document, report	PU - Public	6

¹ R = Report, P = Prototype, D = Demonstrator, DEC = Dissemination-Exploitation-Communication; O = Other; ORPD = Open Research Data Pilot

² PU = Public, PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services), RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services), CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

D6.2	Data Management Plan (DMP)	WP6	1 – UJI	DATA – data sets, microdata, etc	PU - Public	6
D1.1	T-matrix of spheres and pillars	WP1	1 – UJI	R – Document, report	PU - Public	6
D4.1	Low frequency characterisation set-up	WP4	3 – CNRS	DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	SEN - Sensitive	6
D7.2	First dissemination and exploitation plans	WP7	1 – UJI	DEC – Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	PU - Public	6
D3.2	Optimal disordered phononic surface	WP3	2 – CSIC	R – Document, report	SEN - Sensitive	12
D4.2	High frequency characterisation set-up	WP4	3 – CNRS	DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	SEN - Sensitive	12
D5.1	Experimental set up	WP5	1 – UJI	R – Document, report	PU - Public	12
D6.3	Review Meeting Document 1	WP6	1 – UJI	R – Document, report	SEN - Sensitive	13
D4.3	Spatio-temp. maps of optimal pillar samples	WP4	3 – CNRS	DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU - Public	14
D1.3	Equations of eigenvalues of twisted membranes	WP1	1 – UJI	R – Document, report	PU - Public	18

D1.2	Formulation of multiple scattering	WP1	1 – UJI	R – Document, report	PU - Public	24
D1.4	Algorithm for the density of modes	WP1	1 – UJI	R – Document, report	PU - Public	24
D2.1	Most influential features and parameters	WP2	4 - AGH / AGH-UST	R – Document, report	PU - Public	24
D3.3	Optimal twisted architectures	WP3	2 – CSIC	R – Document, report	SEN - Sensitive	24
D5.2	Development of single pixel applications	WP5	1 – UJI	R – Document, report	PU - Public	24
D4.4	Spatio-temp. maps of optimal twisted samples	WP4	3 – CNRS	DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU - Public	28
D2.2	Optimized design algorithms	WP2	4 - AGH / AGH-UST	R – Document, report	SEN - Sensitive	30
D6.6	Data Management Plan (DPM) update	WP6	1 – UJI	R – Document, report	PU - Public	30
D6.4	Review Meeting Document 2	WP6	1 – UJI	R – Document, report	SEN - Sensitive	31
D2.3	Optimal degree of disorder	WP2	4 - AGH / AGH-UST	R – Document, report	SEN - Sensitive	36

D3.4	Optimal final device for imaging	WP3	2 – CSIC	DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU - Public	36
D5.3	Report on imaging capabilities for living WP5 cells	WP5	1 – UJI	R – Document, report	PU - Public	36
D4.5	Characterization of phononic surfaces with SLM	WP4	3 – CNRS	DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU - Public	40
D2.4	Optimal twisted membrane	WP2	4 - AGH / AGH-UST	R – Document, report	SEN - Sensitive	42
D5.4	Report on characterization of phononic WP5 surfaces	WP5	1 – UJI	R – Document, report	PU - Public	48
D6.5	Review Meeting Document 3	WP6	1 – UJI	R – Document, report	SEN - Sensitive	48
D7.3	Final dissemination and exploitation plans	WP7	1 – UJI	DEC – Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	PU - Public	48

Table 3: List of Deliverables

The deliverables must be completed and submitted to the EC according to the timetable specified in the Deliverable list above. All of them must be uploaded and submitted electronically in the Funding & Tenders Portal on the due date.

The WP leader is responsible to the preparation of the correspondent(s) deliverable(s) assigned to their WP. The coordinator shall be responsible for collecting, reviewing to verify consistency, and submitting deliverables. If a delay is detected, the partner responsible should report it to the coordinator, to take the necessary corrective actions and to communicate it to the EC Project Officer. The coordinator may nevertheless submit the other Parties' Project deliverables and all other documents required by the Grant Agreement to the Granting Authority in time.

5.3.Milestones

Milestones may correspond to the completion of a key deliverable, which allows the next phase of the work to begin or is needed at intermediary points. According to the [Online Manual](#), milestones as well as deliverables should be submitted by each participant for their work, by completing the Continuous Reporting Module. In the table below, the list of milestones for the whole project is shown in chronological order, to make it easy to follow up on milestones achievement.

Mil. No	Milestone Name	WP No	Lead Beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date (month)
6	Laser ultrasonic setup operates at 100 MHz	WP4	3-CNRS	Measurement of the displacement field around a test sample	6
7	Programs to calculate the chirped masks ready	WP4	3-CNRS	Fourier analysis of the excited ultrasonic pulses	7
1	General methodology to compute the T- matrix of a scatterer over a phononic surface	WP1	1-UJI	Numerical comparison between scattering properties	24
2	Critical parameters are selected, and the optimization framework is designed, implemented, and validated.	WP2	4-AGH / AGH-UST	Numerical benchmarks verifying performance of the framework.	30
8	Single pixel imaging with a resolution of 8x8	WP5	1-UJI	Report of results	30
4	Moiré phononic architectures	WP3	2-CSIC	Report of their properties	36
3	Optimal phononic surface structural designs found through the inverse problem solution procedure.	WP2	4-AGH / AGH-UST	V&V of the design by direct numerical simulations, fabrication feasibility evaluation and experimental tests.	40
5	Optimized phononic architectures	WP3	2-CSIC	Report of their properties	42
9	Ultra-fast imaging with phononic surfaces	WP5	1-UJI	Report of results	45

Table 4: List of Milestones

6. Project Management

6.1.Management Structure

Within the Dynamo Consortium, each participant will take an active part in the efficient implementation of the project, and will cooperate, perform, and fulfil, promptly and on time, all its obligations as foreseen in the GA.

Three different levels, Strategic, Operational and Advisory, have been defined for the managerial structure of Dynamo to guarantee the compliance of the commitments with the European Commission detailed in the Grant Agreement.

A mailing list in the private intranet of the project website was created including detailed information about the role of partner’s main contacts that should be contacted depending on the purpose of the communication: technical/project issues, administrative and financial issues, and communication and dissemination issues.

The project management structure of Dynamo is described in the Consortium Agreement, in Section 6. The following figure identifies the management structure of the project and the interrelations within it:

Figure 1: Dynamo management structure

6.1.1. Strategic Level

Project Coordinator:

The project coordinator will be represented by **Daniel Torrent, from UJI**, who is responsible for the overall management of the project, the project direction and success. As project coordinator he will be responsible for:

Communication:

- All communications between the project and the Commission, acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority
- Transmit documents and information related to the project to the Partners

Global Monitoring:

- Follow-up and updating of the project planning
- Monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations
- Reporting: collecting, reviewing to verify consistency, and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certification) and specific requested documents to the Granting Authority
- Preparing the meetings, proposing decisions, and preparing the agenda of Project Coordination Committee meetings, chairing the meetings, preparing the minutes of the meetings, and monitoring the implementation of decisions taken at meetings
- Monitoring of the expenses and allocation of the budget; assistance towards the participants concerning administrative aspects of the project
- Coordinating the payments to the partners

Project Coordination Committee:

The Project Coordination Committee (PCC) **is the decision-making body** and shall consist of **one representative of each partner**. The PCC will be free to act on its own initiative to formulate proposals and make decisions in accordance with the procedures set out in the Consortium Agreement.

Among their responsibilities are to advise and support the decisions of the Project Coordinator on operational and management issues as well as be responsible for all decisions of general nature within the frame of the EC Contract and the Consortium Agreement. Especially the detailed budget allocation, any re-definition of the overall work plan, the coordination of the activities and communication between the subgroups, and the overall project progress assessment will be performed by this committee. The detailed responsibilities and tasks are described in the project's Consortium Agreement. The PCC is chaired by the Project Coordinator. The chairperson shall convene ordinary meetings of the Project Coordination Committee at least once every six months and shall also convene extraordinary meetings at any time upon written request of any member.

6.1.2. Operational Level

WP Leaders:

At this level, leaders have been appointed for the seven different Work Packages of Dynamo. Each WP will have **one responsible partner** (WP Leader) that will coordinate:

- WP tasks activities
- coordination of the partners involved in each task
- drafting process of the deliverables
- identification of WP-specific risks

The WP teams are responsible for an effective and efficient implementation of the work associated with a specific work package. The following WP leaders

have been assigned (and take part to the Project Coordination Committee as previously defined):

- WP1: Daniel Torrent (UJI)
- WP2: Pawel Packo (AGH/AGH-UST)
- WP3: Agustín Mihi (CSIC)
- WP4: Bernard Bonello (CNRS)
- WP5: Enrique Tajahuerce (UJI)
- WP6: Daniel Torrent (UJI)
- WP7: Daniel Torrent (UJI)

The role of WP Leaders is essential for the project since they will be responsible for the coordination of the Task Leaders and management of their task(s) and the timely production of the associated deliverables with contributions by task team members. The WP Leaders will regularly report task performance to the coordinator to identify variances against the task objectives/timetable/resource plan, evaluate the overall WP performance, and report to the Project Coordination Committee.

The responsibility of the deliverables to be developed along the project duration lies with the different WP Leaders.

Project Manager:

The project manager will be represented by **Michelle Andrade, from UJI**, and appointed by the Project Coordinator and is under his direct supervision, her role is to assist the work of the coordinator for the day-to-day management. More specifically, the Project Manager role is to:

- Communicate with project partners on a timely basis
- Track project progress against programme objectives
- Prepare technical and financial reports
- Organize teleconferences / project meetings / workshops / conferences
- Have the overall responsibility for the complete management of the project

6.1.3. Advisory Level

Advisory Board

The Advisory Board (AB) shall **support and facilitate the decisions** made by the Project Coordination Committee through high representative profiles in PHOTONICS. A tentative list for this Advisory Board is the following:

- Philip Engel (M, HOLOEYE Photonics AG)
- PhD. Sarah Benchabane (F, FEMTO-ST as a CNRS researcher)
- Prof. Krzysztof M. Abramski (M, Wrocław University of Technology)
- Prof. Sylvain Gigan (M, Sorbonne Université and group leader in Laboratoire Kastler-Brossel at Ecole Normale Supérieure)
- Vicenta Ferrer Chova (F, Nayar Systems)
- Prof. Alastair P Hibbins (Director of the Centre for Metamaterial Research and Innovation, Exeter)

The Advisory Board will play an important advisory and consultative role in Dynamo. The main goals of this board will be the following:

- Providing advice and feedback to the project objectives.

- Monitoring the main milestones of the project, updating their feedback, and providing the necessary inputs for guiding the project towards the achievement of the objectives.
- Providing final feedback on results evaluation and expectations for future evolution.
- Assist and facilitate decisions made by the consortium.

6.2. Project Management Procedures

6.2.1. General Management Procedures

Partners of Dynamo are responsible for:

- Effective economic and financial management and the success of the operational work in accordance with the proposal and with ethical and legal standards.
- Complying with general terms and conditions specific to the granting programme established by the European Commission, the Grant Agreement, and the Consortium Agreement.
- Managing and supervising operational personnel.
- Meeting reporting requirements.

The roles and responsibilities of each Consortium Body are defined in the project Consortium Agreement.

Decision Taking Mechanism

Decisions should be taken always at the right decision level. In this sense, decisions will be taking according to the following parameters:

- One member of each party shall act as a representative.
- Each Member present or represented in the meeting shall have one vote.
- Decisions shall be taken by a majority of three-fourths (3/4) of the votes cast, otherwise it will be not valid.

Project Meetings

The regular meetings will ensure a proper and continuous communication between the partners, efficient monitoring of project activities and timely identification of risks and contingency plans. Meetings are classified into the following categories:

- WP progress online meetings: These meetings will involve at least two partners of the project, and should include WP leader, and if necessary, the Project Coordination Committee. They will be held every two months to monitor and verify the work progress of the respective WP
- WPs coordination online meeting: These meetings will involve WP leaders and Project coordinator.
- Annual WPs and plenary meeting: once a year a plenary meeting will be held in a different location considering Project development activities. During this same plenary meeting, different focus groups will carry out separate WP-specific meetings to debate and discuss the relevant topics, to address ongoing activities and to plan the work for the subsequent period.

The first plenary meeting (Kick-off Meeting) was held in Castelló at M3. The calendar of the three remaining annual meetings is to be defined yet. Three further meetings are expected:

- 2nd Annual Meeting, in March 2023 (M13) in Paris, France
- 3rd Annual Meeting, in September 2024 (M31) in Krakow, Poland or Barcelona, Spain
- Final Meeting, between February 2026 (on M48) in Brussels, Belgium

6.2.2. Innovation Management and IPR Procedures

Intellectual property rights, results and background are regulated in Article 16 as well as some specific rules are set out in Annex 5 of the GA.

Management of knowledge and protection of intellectual property has priority over dissemination as it facilitates exploitation and maximizes project value. Innovation management will be done through systematic evaluation of the work done. Every partner will be advised by their Office for Technological Innovation Activities, the supporting services for the management of the scientific and technological knowledge generated by researchers in terms of R&D&I. The Consortium has a strict policy of checking if results can be protected before publishing, which involves screening the results for novelty and if potential novel concepts are found, a novelty check will be performed and based on the results from that and the potential uses foreseen for the new technology, a decision on patent application will be made. The key consideration will always be to maximize the project value.

The beneficiaries must comply with the additional IPR, dissemination and exploitation obligations set out in the call conditions, in particular:

- **use the EIC Market Place platform** to exchange information on results (including preliminary findings) and Portfolio activities, in accordance with the Terms and Conditions of that platform. Including simultaneous unrestricted dissemination of results through the EIC Market Place
- **provide updates to the plan for exploitation and dissemination of the results** and information on dissemination or exploitation activities, if requested by the granting authority and for up to four years after the end of the action

Partner responsibilities, rights and obligations, dissemination and exploitation policy, management of knowledge and IP issues and access to results has been described in the Consortium Agreement (CA) that has been signed by all Dynamo partners.

6.2.3. Payment Procedures

Payments to be made

Data Sheet, point 4.2 and Articles 21 and 22 to the Grant Agreement establishes the payments to be made from the European Commission to the Coordinator, and from the coordinator to the rest of the consortium:

- One Pre-financing payment³: 1,352,707.08 €
- Two Interim payments: up to 90% of the maximum grant amount
- Final payment/ payment of balance: reimburses the remaining part of the eligible costs and contributions claimed for the implementation of the action (if any)

Interim payments & Final payment

Interim payments reimburse the eligible costs for the implementation of the action during the corresponding reporting periods. Payment is subject to the approval of the periodic report. The deadline (time to pay) is 90 days from receiving the periodic report.

There will be up to three more payments of contribution from the coordinator to the beneficiaries. The deadline for the payments is:

- Interim payment of PR1: estimated in M17 (July 2023)
- Interim payment of PR2: estimated in M35 (January 2025)
- Final payment: estimated in M53 (July 2026)

7. Project Reporting

7.1. Internal Reporting

Monitoring the project implementation is a continuous task during the whole period of the project and beyond.

Each WP leader must report the project progress to the coordinator every six months. Documents to be sent to the coordinator to elaborate the internal reports are including at the end of this Handbook and are the following:

- Annex I. Six-monthly Technical Report Template
- Annex II. Six-monthly Communication and Dissemination Report Template
- Annex III. Six-monthly Financial Report Template

WP leaders will explain how they contribute to the technical progress, results, deliverables, and compliance with the WP schedule, as well as the monitoring and updating of the potential risks.

The WP Leader will be supported in all the processes and be validated by the project coordinator and the Project Coordination Committee.

7.2. External Reporting to the EC

7.2.1. Periodic Reports

In order to receive payments, the consortium must submit the periodic and final reports to the EC, following the schedule set out in the Data Sheet, section 4.2:

- 1st Periodic Report covering the activity from month 1 to month 12: from 01/03/2022 to 28/02/2023

³ **Mutual Insurance Mechanism (MIM) contribution:** an amount corresponding to 5% of the maximum grant amount (127,613.88€), is retained by the European Commission from the pre- financing payment and transferred into the 'Guarantee Fund.

- 2nd Periodic Report covering the activity from month 13 to month 30: from 01/03/2023 to 31/08/2024
- 3rd or Final Report covering the activity from month 31 to month 48: from 01/09/2024 to 28/02/2026

Submission of periodic reports and final report

The periodic report should be prepared by the consortium participants together and it will be submitted as a single report by the coordinator directly in the Periodic Reporting Module of the Portal Grant Management System.

As stated in the Grant Agreement, the two periodic reports and the final report shall be submitted to the Commission by the coordinator within 60 days after the end of the reporting period.

- 1st Periodic report shall be delivered in M14 – deadline 30/04/2023
- 2nd Periodic report shall be delivered in M32 – deadline 31/10/2024
- Final report shall be delivered in M50 – deadline 30/04/2026

If the granting authority does not receive the report within the deadline, only costs and contributions which are included in an approved periodic report will be considered (no costs/contributions if no periodic report was ever approved).

Content of periodic reports

The content of the Periodic Reports is determined by the Commission in accordance with Article 21.2 of the Grant Agreement and the [Online Manual](#). The structure of the Periodic Report contains the technical and financial report, and it is as follows:

The **Technical Report**, includes an overview of the action implementation, and is itself also divided in two parts, Parts A and B:

- Part A: contains the structured tables with project information. The IT tool will capture the information from the Continuous Reporting Module and will generate this part.
- Part B (the narrative part): mirrors the application form and requires the participants to report on differences (delays, work not implemented, new subcontracts, budget overruns etc.) It needs to be prepared outside the tools (using the template downloaded from the system) and then uploaded as PDF (together with Annexes, if any).

The **Financial Report** includes:

- The Individual Financial Statements (individual and consolidated; for all beneficiaries/affiliated entities). It will be retrieved from the Continuous Reporting Module. All beneficiaries shall electronically complete the model via the Funding and Tenders Portal and shall be signed electronically by the corresponding Project Financial Signatories (PFSIGN) appointed by each organization.
- An explanation on the use of resources. It should be complete in the Continuous Reporting Module (or detailed cost reporting table, excel table - if required)

- Certificates on the financial statements (CFS) (if required; see Article 24.2 and Data Sheet, Point 4.3). It must be prepared using the template available in the Reference Documents section on the Funding & Tenders Portal. Conditions for the CFS:
 - o Schedule: only at final payment, if threshold is reached.
 - o Standard threshold (beneficiary-level): requested EU contribution to costs \geq EUR 430 000.00

Technical information: workflow.

The process for collecting these inputs is detailed below:

Figure 2. Technical information – workflow

The Project Coordinator will launch the process of collecting technical inputs for the technical report at the end of M12 (28/02/2023), M30 (31/08/2024), M48 (28/02/2026).

Financial information: workflow.

The process for collecting these inputs will be supervised by the coordinator and is detailed below:

Figure 3. Financial information - workflow

The Project Coordinator will launch the process of collecting inputs for the financial report at the end of M12 (28/02/2023), M30 (31/08/2024), M48 (28/02/2026).

Documents to be sent to the coordinator to elaborate the periodic reports are the following:

Report	Author	Data issue	Deadline
Technical Report	Work Package Leader	Contribution to the deliverables and technical reports	One month after finalization of each reporting period: M13, M31 and M48
Financial Report	All partners	Explanation on the use of resources	One month after finalization of each reporting period: M13, M31 and M48
	All the partners (beneficiaries/ affiliated entity)	The financial statements. + Certificate on Financial Statements (CFS) (if required, see Articles 21 and 24.2 and Data Sheet, Point 4.3)	One month after finalization of each reporting period: M13, M31 and M48

Table 5: Inputs for the periodic report

If the deadline for the internal and external reporting is the same, only the external reports should be prepared by the WP leader and submitted by the coordinator. The following table summarizes the periods reported, the documents to be prepared and the deadlines for submission.

Type of Report	Period Reported	Deadline for submission	Data issue
1 st Internal Report	M1 - M6 01/03/2022 to 31/08/2022	M8 31/10/2022	Annex I, Annex II and Annex III
1st Periodic Report	M1 - M12 01/03/2022 to 28/02/2023	M14 30/04/2023	Technical and Financial Report
2 nd Internal Report	M13 - M18 01/03/2023 to 31/08/2023	M20 31/10/2023	Annex I, Annex II and Annex III
3 rd Internal Report	M19 - M24 01/09/2023 to 29/02/2024	M26 30/04/2024	Annex I, Annex II and Annex III
2nd Periodic Report	M13 - M30 01/03/2023 to 31/08/2024	M32 31/10/2024	Technical and Financial Report
4 th Internal Report	M31 - M36 01/09/2024 to 28/02/2025	M38 30/04/2025	Annex I, Annex II and Annex III
5 th Internal Report	M37 - M42 01/03/2025 to 31/08/2025	M44 31/10/2025	Annex I, Annex II and Annex III
Final report	M31 - M48 01/09/2024 to 28/02/2026	M50 30/04/2026	Technical and Financial Report

Table 6: Periods and deadlines for internal and external reporting

Continuous reporting

Apart from the project reporting obligations, it should be provided regular updates on the status of the project: the continuous reporting. The coordinator will complete the Project Continuous Report online tool via the electronic exchange system (SyGMA).

This tool makes available the online submission of Deliverables and Periodic Reporting information that can be optionally entered at any time during the life of the project such as:

- Publishable project summary
- Submit deliverables
- Report progress in achieving milestones
- Follow up critical risks
- Questionnaire on horizontal issues:
 - o Dissemination activities
 - o Communications activities
 - o Financial support to 3rd parties

All this information is automatically compiled to create part A of the periodic Technical Report.

7.2.2. Report on the distribution of payments

According to the Article 7 of the Grant Agreement, the coordinator must inform EC about the payments made to the other beneficiaries (if required, see Articles 22 and 32).

If the balance of the final payment is negative, the EC will send a pre-information letter to the coordinator formally notifying the intention to recover, the final grant amount, (Article 22) the amount to be recovered and the reasons why. The coordinator must prepare and submit a report on the distribution of payments to the beneficiaries within 30 days of receiving notification.

Also, if the GA or beneficiary termination happens (Article 32) the coordinator must, within 60 days from when termination takes effect, submit a report on the distribution of payments to the beneficiary concerned.

7.2.3. Project reviews

The granting authority may carry out reviews, may be assisted by outside experts, on the proper implementation of the action and compliance with the obligations (Article 25 of the GA). In the DoA, 3 project reviews are mentioned. The dates and location for them are the following:

Review No.	Timing (month)	Location
RV1	14	Brussels (tbc)
RV2	31	Brussels (tbc)
RV3	49	Brussels (tbc)

Table 7: List of project reviews

The coordinator or beneficiary concerned have the following **rights and obligations**:

- Be informed about the review
- Be requested to participate in meetings
- Have the right to object on grounds of commercial confidentiality or conflict of interest, to replace the outside expert
- Cooperate and provide directly to the grant authority, within the deadline requested, any information and data in addition to deliverables and reports already submitted (including information on the use of resources)
- Provided accurate, precise, and complete information and in the format requested, including electronic format

And they are **obligated to**:

- Keep records and other supporting documentation for 5 years (Data Sheet, Section 6).
- Make available all the records and documents during checks, reviews, audits, or investigations and to keep them until the end of these procedures.
- Keep original documents or authorized digital copies

8. Information Management

8.1. Document Management

The management procedures guarantee that the project's documents are produced, updated, distributed, and stored correctly and efficiently.

The official documentation repository for the Dynamo project is accessible through its private intranet in the project website (<https://dynamo-project.eu/>).

This website contains a public part and a private intranet. The public part of the project website acts as a dissemination channel. The private part contains sections to store the document repository needed by the partners during the project. A summary of the documentation organization is given below:

Management menu:

- Documents section:
- Contractual documents, including the Grant Agreement with EC and its annexes and the Consortium Agreement with its annexes.
- Guidelines and manuals:
 - [EU Financial Regulation 2018/1046](#)
 - [EIC Work Programme 2021 - Annex 7 Additional provisions concerning Intellectual Property for Pathfinder and Transition actions](#)
 - [European Innovation Council \(EIC\) EIC Fund Investment Guidelines](#)
 - [Project reporting templates](#)
 - [Communication toolkit for EIC funding schemes](#)
- Contact list: Access to the updated contact list of all project partners

- Templates: Access to the updated and official EC templates related to the project.
- Material created for communications (leaflets, roll-ups, photos, etc)
- Meetings and events (list of meetings and link to the events page in the project website)
- Work packages folders
- WP Gantt chart
- WP Internal documents
- WP deliverables

8.2. Technical Information Management

The WP leaders and the coordinator are key figures in the management of the technical information within the project.

All issues concerning task progress should be communicated from each supporting partner to the Work Package Leader. The Work Package Leader will be responsible for dealing with the issue and solving it. In the case that the issue cannot be solved, it shall be transmitted to the coordinator.

The coordinator will resolve the issues proposed by the WP Leaders or will transmit them to the Project Coordination Committee if it is necessary.

Figure 4. Technical information flow chart

Review and Submission of Deliverables

The consortium must continuously report on the progress of the action through deliverables. The WP leaders are responsible for the generation of the deliverable and for the technical quality of the deliverables.

All the deliverables must be successfully completed and submitted to the European Commission, electronically via the Portal Continuous Reporting tool, in accordance with the timing and conditions it sets out in Annex I to the Grant Agreement.

Standardized deliverables (e.g., progress reports not linked to payments, reports on cumulative expenditure, special reports, etc; if any) must be submitted using the templates published on the Funding and Tenders Portal:

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/reference-documents;programCode=HORIZON>

To guarantee the quality of the deliverables to be submitted, they must meet the following requirements:

- Fulfil the objectives as set out in the WP description in Annex I

- Justify the resources expended as outlined in the progress reports
- Verify the format/ template used is correct

Also, the procedure has been defined as following:

- **6 weeks in advance** to the planned delivery date for each deliverable, the Project Manager will contact the WP leader in charge of the deliverable to check whether it will be submitted as planned or whether there is any unexpected problem that may cause a substantial delay. In case of delay, the Project Manager will communicate the issue to the coordinator, to analyse how to solve the problem and, if necessary, the coordinator will inform the EU Project Officer and he will ask for a new date for submission of the deliverable as soon as possible.
- **At least 2 weeks** before the submission of the deliverable, the WP leader responsible for the generation of the deliverable will send the deliverable to the coordinator and the supporting partners, defined for each deliverable according to the Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement. There will be at least 1 week for collecting comments/suggestions from the supporting partners, which can be included or not in the deliverable document.
- **At least 3 working days** before the submission deadline, the partner responsible for the deliverable concerned will send the final version to the coordinator.
- The coordinator will be responsible for submitting the deliverables to the European Commission.

Figure 5. Deliverable revision and submission process

If a submission deadline is in August or December, the internal deadlines for the revision and submission process may vary, and the coordinator may require receiving the final version of the document in advance to ensure that the revision process is completed by all partners.

The deliverable number and name will follow the Deliverables list numbering and name included in DoA. The delivery number shall be used as a code on the front page of all deliverables.

8.3. Administrative Information Management

By administrative information it is understood any information related to the administrative procedures of the project, including financial issues. Information related to the beneficiaries participating in the project is also part of the administrative information of the project and any changes in this information (legal information, change of name of the organization, change of authorized representatives of each organization, etc.) must be transmitted as soon as possible to the Project Manager to take the necessary measures.

If an issue cannot be resolved by the Project Manager, the Project Coordinator will be informed and asked for assistance. The Project Coordinator will resolve any issues put up by the Project Manager or communicate them to the Project Coordination Committee or Project Officer, if necessary.

8.4. Templates

All the official documents of Dynamo (presentations, deliverables, external communication, meeting minutes, etc.) must use the templates which will be available in the private intranet in the project website. The project logo, the EU emblem and the EIC logo must be included in all the documents related to the project and communication material (prototypes, leaflets, posters etc.).

This is what it should look like:

In addition, EIC logo should also be displayed:

Figure 6. European Union and European Innovation Council Logos

The **emblem** should be accompanied by a funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate).

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA). Neither the European Union nor European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA) can be held responsible for them”.

The templates will be updated during the lifecycle of the project; thus, it is recommended to download the updated templates from the website.

9. Project Changes and Potential Risks

9.1. Project Changes: Amendments / Information Letter

Amendments to the Grant Agreement may reflect the need to adapt to the changing conditions for implementation of the action. The Article 39 and Annex 5 of the G.A mention the conditions of an amendment process:

- The parties (beneficiary or granting authority) may request an amendment to reorient the action (including its objectives or substantial changes affecting the objectives), if required by a change of circumstances and provided that the action remains eligible under the call for which it was selected.
- Investment component: amendment to add the investment component into the Data Sheet, point 1 and Articles 1 and 3 and to adapt the description of the action in Annex 1 and add the investment agreement as Annex 6
- Amendments can only be done in writing
- Any project amendment is subject to official acceptance by the EIC
- Coordinator submits and receives requests for amendment on behalf of the beneficiaries
- Coordinator strongly recommends the partners to check with the project coordinator any issue that might be subject to an amendment
- If a change of coordinator is requested without its agreement, the submission must be done by another beneficiary (acting on behalf of the other beneficiaries).
- The party requesting an amendment must submit a request for amendment signed directly in the Portal Amendment tool

An amendment enters into force on the day of the signature of the receiving party. An amendment takes effect on the date of entry into force or other date specified in the amendment.

The official amendment guide will be available soon, and the participants will have access to it in the private intranet in the Dynamo website.

Changes which do NOT require an Amendment

Changes which do not require an amendment but shall be duly notified to the Commission via an information letter are the following:

- Budget transfers covered by the budget flexibility
- Name or address changes of a participant, will be done directly in the Participant Register
- Universal takeovers (merger/acquisition) of a participant, will be done directly in the Participant Register
- Changes of the banking details, will be done directly in the Participant Register

9.2. Potential Risks

The main potential problem for the project is the case that beneficiaries fail to live up to contractual obligations, in particular deliverables due as described in

the DoA. Such problems will be dealt with by the Project Coordination Committee, when identified.

Any Partner of the Consortium must inform the WP Leader of any potential inconveniences identified. The WP Leader will duly inform the Coordinator and the Project Coordination Committee, if required, to solve the issue.

Dynamo uses a **Risk Register**, which is the central repository for all identified project risks and is used as the main tool to support the Risk Management process. The Risk Register will be updated by the Project Manager with inputs received mainly from risk owners and Work Package Leaders. In practice, the Dynamo Risk Register consists of an Excel spreadsheet that is available to all consortium members through the project internal repository.

An initial list of risks had been identified at the project proposal phase by the consortium members and was included in the DoA. The list has been updated and enriched with information provided by the WP Leaders to be converted into the current Risk Register form. The risks that have been identified during the first months of the project implementation and are presented below.

Risk No.	Description	WP No.	Likelihood	Proposed Mitigation Measures
1	Analytical expressions for the scattering of waves by pillars not found	1	Low	Use fast numerical algorithms to numerically compute the scattering properties or use thinner pillars if possible
2	Calculations of disordered and twisted systems too slow	1	Low	In this case we will use large computation clusters for the calculations
3	Optimization framework computationally not effective enough	2	Medium	Domain decomposition and/or model separation methods can be combined with HPC clusters and supercomputing units to address this issue.
4	Optimal metastructures too complex to fabricate	2	Medium	Compromise the design and fabrication capabilities based on the sensitivity analysis performed earlier. Introduce further fabrication-motivated constraints to the optimization framework.
5	Fabricated phononic crystal show poor response or too complex	3	Low	Disorder surfaces or other previously designed surfaces can be fabricated by EBL and replicated with soft lithography
6	Unexpected delays in fabrication	3	Low	Many kinds of nanostructures can be provided readily from the beginning of the project. ICMAB masters soft lithography, nanosphere lithography and metal and dielectric chemical synthesis. Alternatives will always be available
7	Irreversible damage to the polymer samples	4	Medium	Deposit a thin metallic layer on top of the samples to reduce the amount of

	during illumination by laser pulses			absorbed light. The simulations must account for this additional layer
8	The time required to record the displacement field (time and position) is too long	4	High	Reduce the probing area or decrease the spatial resolution
9	Algorithm to find the maximum number of resonances for a given configuration not found	1,2	Medium	In this case we will consider that this number is equal to the number of scatterers in the cluster, and we will work on this basis
10	Optimal samples not suitable for imaging applications	5	High	This is indeed the highest risk of the project. In this case we will propose the devices for other applications less demanding, like shape recognition, speckle generators, etc.

Table 8: List of risks and mitigation measures

10. Annex I. Six-monthly Technical Report Template

Date of submission: DD.MM.YYYY

This document includes information about the technical progress, results obtained (e.g., deliverables) and compliance with the work programme of the WP (insert number of the WP) in this reporting period.

WP Leader:	
------------	--

Task No.	Partners involved	Objectives	Activities	Results
T.X.1		Describe briefly the objective(s) related with this task and the correspondent activity.	Describe briefly the activities carried out	Describe briefly the preliminary results obtained
T.X.2				
T.X.n				

Deliverables
Indicate if any deliverable was obtained
Short-term Action Plan
Describe briefly the activities that will be done during the next 6 months

Deviations and Potential Risk	
Technical deviations	Describe briefly the identified deviations
Potential Risk	Describe briefly the identified potential risks

11. Annex II. Six-monthly Communication and Dissemination Report Template⁴

Date of submission: DD.MM.YYYY

⁴ All participants must complete this template under the supervision of the WP7 Leader.

This document includes information about the communication and dissemination activities in this reporting period.

Participant:	
--------------	--

Reported Activities (activities done in the last 6 months)

Communication Activities							
Activity name and description (WHAT)	Target Audience (WHO)	Size of audience	Date (WHEN)	Status of the activity	Country (ies) (WHERE)	Channel/ Tool (HOW)	Quantitative & Qualitative Indicators (KPI)
				<i>(Planned, ongoing, finished)</i>			

Short-term Action Plan (proposed activities for the next 6 months)

Communication Activities							
Activity name and description (WHAT)	Target Audience (WHO)	Size of audience	Date (WHEN)	Status of the activity	Country (ies) (WHERE)	Channel/ Tool (HOW)	Quantitative & Qualitative Indicators (KPI)
				<i>(Planned, ongoing, finished)</i>			

Reported Activities (activities done in the last 6 months)

Dissemination Activities						
Activity name and description (WHAT)	Target Audience (WHO)	Size of the audience	Date (WHEN)	Status of the activity	Expected outcomes	Foreseen Impacts
				<i>(Planned, ongoing, finished)</i>		

Short-term Action Plan (proposed activities for the next 6 months)

Dissemination Activities						
Activity name and description (WHAT)	Target Audience (WHO)	Size of the audience	Date (WHEN)	Status of the activity	Expected outcomes	Foreseen Impacts
				<i>(Planned, ongoing, finished)</i>		

12. Annex III. Six-monthly Financial Report Template

Dynamo Interim Financial Report								
Partner:	Universitat Jaume I (UJI)							
Reporting Period:	March22 - Aug22							
6M REPORT								
	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	SUM
A. Personnel (PM)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
A. Personnel (Costs)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
B. Subcontracting								
C. Purchase								
C.1. Travel and subsistence								
C.2. Equipment								
C.3. Other good, work and services								
D. Other cost categories								
D.2. Internally invoiced goods and services								
Total Direct Cost	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
E. Indirect Cost	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total Budget	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
EC Contribution	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Expenditures for the reference period (EURO)								
A. Personnel costs								
Nr.	Total effort (Person months)	Personnel costs (€)						
WP1								
WP2								
WP3								
WP4								
WP5								
WP6								
WP7								
Total	0	- €						
B. Subcontracting								
Item Nr.	Description	Amount spent (€)	Related to WP	Foreseen in Annex 1?	Explanations (if not foreseen in Annex 1)			
1								
2								
3								
4								
		Total:	- €					
C. Purchase Costs								
C.1. Travel and Subsistence								
Item Nr.	Travel period (DD.MM.YY - DD.MM.YY)	No. of traveller	Place travelled to	Reason for travelling	Cost of Travel (€)	Related to WP		
1								
2								
3								
4								
5								
6								
					Total:	- €		
C.2. Equipment								
Item Nr.	Description	Amount spent (€)	Related to WP	Foreseen in Annex 1?	Explanations (if not foreseen in Annex 1)			
1								
2								
3								
4								
		Total:	- €					
C.3. Other goods, works and services								
Item Nr.	Description	Amount spent (€)	Related to WP	Foreseen in Annex 1?	Explanations (if not foreseen in Annex 1)			
1								
2								
3								
4								
5								
6								
		Total:	- €					
D. Other cost categories								
D.2. Internally invoiced goods and services								
Item Nr.	Description	Amount spent (€)	Related to WP	Foreseen in Annex 1?	Explanations (if not foreseen in Annex 1)			
1								
2								
3								
4								
5								
6								
		Total:	- €					

13. Annex IV. Deliverable Template

**INSERT THE TITLE OF THE
DELIVERABLE**

Date: Day Month Year

D.X.X: Deliverable Number and Title

WPx. T.X.X: WP's Number and Title

Author(s) and ORCID(s) ID: Name and Surnames of the author 1 (ORCID ID 1); Name and Surnames of the author 2 (ORCID ID 2); ...; Name and Surnames of the author X (ORCID ID X).

Dynamo Title of the document

Universitat Jaume I

Contact Daniel Torrent, Coordinator of the Dynamo project

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Technical References

Project General Information

Project Number	101046489
Project Acronym	Dynamo
Project Title	Dynamic Spatio-Temporal Modulation of Light by Phononic Architectures
Granting Authority	European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency
Call	HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN-01
Topic	HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN-01-01
Type of the Action	HORIZON EIC Grants
Duration	1 March 2022 - 28 February 2026 (48 months)
Entry into force of the Grant	1 March 2022
Project Coordinator	Daniel Torrent Martí

Deliverable No.	DX.X
Work Package	WPX – Title of the WP
Task	TX.X - Title of the task
Dissemination level*	PU – Public/ CO - Confidential
Lead beneficiary	Universitat Jaume I
PIC of the Lead beneficiary	999882985
Contributing beneficiary/ies	Name of the contributing organization(s)
PIC of the Contributing beneficiary/ies	PIC of the contributing organization(s)
Due date of deliverable	DD MM YYYY
Actual submission date	DD MM YYYY

Version History

Version	Date	Beneficiary	Author
V1	DD/MM/YYYY	Name of the organization	Name and Surname(s) of the author(s)
	Date	Beneficiary	Reviewed by
V2	DD/MM/YYYY	Name of the organization	Name and Surname(s) of the reviewers(s)
	Date	Beneficiary	Approved by
V3	DD/MM/YYYY	Name of the organization	Name and Surname(s) of the approval person

Table of Contents

Introduction

Executive Summary

Description of the document.